

IMPORTANT ISSUES OF PROVIDING INFORMATION SECURITY IN FORMING THE SPIRITUAL AND MORAL QUALITIES OF STUDENTS IN PRIMARY EDUCATION

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Abstract. *A person with spiritual and moral qualities is consistent with the concept of a perfect person. Samples of folklore in primary school textbooks serve as an important resource for the formation of moral and moral qualities in students.*

Keywords: *children, patriotism, sense of responsibility, formation, morals, spirituality, examples of folklore, information security.*

Introduction

It is our main task to lead students to spiritual and moral elevation, to open the door of knowledge to them. A person with spiritual and moral qualities is consistent with the concept of a perfect person. At the same time, this concept is connected with the concept of a healthy generation. Although these concepts are used separately in scientific literature, in essence they all cover human morals and manners, all the positive qualities formed in them, from their relationship to people, society and the Motherland, to family, parents and others. . At this point, a natural question arises: what should a person with spiritual and moral qualities be like? A person with spiritual and moral qualities is consistent with the concept of a perfect person. At the same time, this concept is connected with the concept of a healthy generation. Although these concepts are used separately in scientific literature, in essence they all cover human morals and manners, all the positive qualities formed in them, from their relationship to people, society and the Motherland, to family, parents and others. At this point, a natural question arises: what should a person with spiritual and moral qualities be like? The formation of moral and moral perfection and pride, national pride in young people has been the focus of attention of progressive thinkers at all times. For example, the great scholar of the East, Abu Rayhan Beruni, writes: "Pride is actually going ahead in good manners and noble actions, acquiring knowledge and wisdom, and purifying oneself from existing impurities as much as possible. Whoever has these qualities, his behavior will be in his favor, and whoever lacks them, his behavior will be against him".

Research materials and methodology.

The neighborhood, educational institutions, family, mass media, youth organizations, state organizations and public associations are responsible for educating a person with moral and moral qualities. Educating primary school students in the spirit of national values based on high spirituality, in particular, forming spiritual and moral virtues in their minds and thinking is planting the seeds of goodness in the spiritual and mental world of a person. Accordingly, it can be said that spirituality is a set of concepts embodying the inner life, spiritual experiences, mental abilities and perception of society and the nation, in general, of each person. Our main tasks in educating a person with spiritual and moral qualities are to form a sense of patriotism and responsibility in children, to explain to children that morality is the basis of spirituality, to raise children with high

spirituality and faith, to teach children about the Motherland. development of a sense of pride, explaining the negative effects of "mass culture" attacks in children's language, educating them in the spirit of nationality, traditions and values. The period of primary education is a certain stage of personal development and maturation, and is a bridge between childhood and adulthood.

Samples of folklore in primary school textbooks serve as an important resource for the formation of moral and moral qualities in students. Analytical results of primary educational programs show that new generation textbooks have great potential in forming moral and moral qualities in students of the 1st and 4th grades.

Search results. At a time when Uzbekistan is entering the ranks of developed countries with bold steps, our textbooks serve to instill in students the desire to be proud of their homeland, country, country, and strive to be children worthy of this country, it is our national heritage. import of folklore materials would be the same term. It is gratifying that proverbs and riddles, which serve to form spiritual and moral qualities in students, are expressed in today's elementary school textbooks. The use of works of well-known writers and poets of Uzbek literature also gives positive results in education of spiritual and moral qualities in primary school students. The natural environment plays an important role in the positive resolution of goals and tasks related to the formation of spiritual and moral qualities in elementary school students. Because the effectiveness of teacher-student cooperation depends on the natural environment.

- organization of lesson processes through 4K skills and "role models";
- Also, activities in cooperation with parents help to develop the child's learning and abilities. Directing children to spend their free time effectively;
- Increasing respect for family - neighbors, parents, teachers through narration, story, and hadith
- Raising respect for our national values by organizing trips to our national monuments in our country;
- Organizing "Three Generation Meetings" in cooperation with family, neighborhood, educational institution, "Inviting representatives of the older generation to classes, organizing INTERVIEW classes;
- First of all, the curiosity of a primary school student is directed towards studying the environment. The child experiences through the game, observes the causes and results of the processes. The teacher must teach to distinguish between good and bad.

Work is being carried out on forming the necessary skills of primary school students, raising the quality of primary education to a new level, and implementing modern teaching methods and tools. The main goal of primary education: the child's positive attitude to reading, reading literacy, which is the most necessary today, working with various information, knowing the basic mathematical operations and being able to apply them in everyday life , consists of forming such skills as logical and creative thinking, self-management, self-control in a team, mastering the rules of written and oral communication culture, organizing educational activities. The professional potential and level of education of a primary school teacher, knowledge of child psychology, modern primary education methods are important in improving the quality of primary education. It is desirable to form the necessary skills in primary school students, raise the quality and efficiency of primary education to a new level, and introduce modern teaching methods and tools into practice. These methodical manuals were published and applied to the educational process in order to improve the quality and efficiency of primary education in all secondary schools

of our republic, and now multimedia discs, the effective results of the methodical manual are published in the mass media. is being recognized.

Based on the capabilities and needs of primary school students, the teacher can approach his work creatively, make changes to the lesson plans given in this manual, and use the tasks given in the manual and multimedia applications in other lessons. Multimedia is the creation, storage, processing and production of various information in digital form. Multimedia: texts, pictures, charts, diagrams, photographs, graphics, audio recordings. Multimedia technologies make it possible to present knowledge in various forms with the help of a computer: voice recording, sound effects and music, images, including scanned images, drawings, maps and slides, video, complex video effects and animated imitations, animations and simulations. Tasks necessary to achieve the effectiveness of the work carried out in this direction today:

Discussions. Organization of systematic training in "Schools of Skills" for the formation of skills and competences in the use of multimedia applications and manuals in primary education teachers, for the use of ICT in primary classes and its effectiveness to improve the material and technical base of each classroom and to equip these classrooms at the level of modern requirements, to take measures to organize the effective use of information and communication technologies, educational and methodological resources, technical means of teaching delivered to educational institutions , in particular, to organize training sessions with teachers on the effective use of equipment. New state education based on the competence approach based on the qualitative approach of the new state education standards and training programs based on the competence approach in the subjects of general secondary education standards, proposals for improvement of educational programs are thoroughly discussed in methodological associations and delivered to the Republican Education Center by the decision of the council;

Methodological provision and organization of the activities of educational institutions, organization of discussion and popularization of best practices in science and methodical associations established under district (city) departments;

to ensure regular participation of teachers in training in "Schools of Skills" on method days in their subjects; analyze the use of advanced pedagogical and information and communication technologies by teachers, as well as methodical manuals created by the Ministry and their multimedia applications, once a month;

to ensure that the effectiveness of primary education teachers' use of advanced pedagogical and information and communication technologies and methodical manuals created by the ministry and their multimedia applications is taken into account in the process of setting bonuses and incentives; strictly put an end to the practice of appointing students whose students did not show high results, who do not have prestige in the school, to the leadership of the method association.

Also, it is necessary to pay special attention to organizing the use of the Internet system by students in the formation of legal education in the education of a person with spiritual and moral qualities in primary education. The Internet allows students to search, find, use materials from the information space, and choose certain variable actions. This, in turn, creates an interactive interaction of information.

Interactivity is the choice of the user's options for active interaction with the information carrier, changing the speed of transmission. The network system removes not only territorial, but also age-related boundaries. A student can engage with older people, and adults can play online games suitable for children. In most of the network system, children of 1st, 2nd, 3rd grade can also

play some military games, shooting or war games, or animated games where a hunter shoots animal and the more animals he shoots, the more points he gets. We are witnessing what they are doing. As a result, it is clear that nervous tension and fatigue in a child have a negative effect on his psyche. Therefore, teachers of primary education, parents in the family should prevent and monitor this situation in the child. For example, in Germany, the articles of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights were presented to children in a very simple manner in a recently multiplied film on the German television channel "Deutsche Welle". For example, the fact that a person has the right to live, that he has the right to work inside the house, and the right to work, from planting a tree to building a building, were expressed with interesting pictures. As a result, we adults also watched this cartoon with interest. They advertised on television that this cartoon could be obtained from the rights site of the Internet network. From a young age, the child is being taught his legal rights and obligations in an interesting way. It would be appropriate if we used such methods and technologies.

Teachers and pedagogues should explain the following requirements to elementary school students when using the Internet for the first time. efficient use of the search system and catalogs, finding the necessary information according to the purpose, explaining the information, understanding to whom the information is directed - storing information and using it correctly in everyday life, information resources on the network, rational use of the computer.

Conclusion. If the student knows all of the above, he will be able to work on the network later. Students can protect themselves from the harmful aspects of the Internet. After acquiring the necessary intellectual knowledge, students will be able to move to the stage of effective use of networking. With the help of a teacher, it is necessary to ensure that legal education gradually passes from simplicity to complexity in primary education. For example: in the process of teaching legal education, the teacher should note that legal information is provided to students mainly under the "Law" site, and explain the procedure for using this site. It is necessary to indicate the existence of such sites as "Legal Education", "Legal Education", "Legal Culture", "International Law" under this site. Having information about them allows students to respect legal knowledge and acquire legal knowledge independently, and in addition, it develops the culture of correct use of the Internet. The conclusion is that in the formation of spiritual and moral education in the form of students of junior school age, the enlightener Abdurauf Fitrat's "The task of moral education" is to bring a person to moral perfection and to educate him as a useful person for society. In order to achieve this goal, first of all, encourage children to physical and mental education, then explain the moral powers through discussion, make them accustomed to good deeds, hate bad deeds, promotion should be the priority goal of our professional activity.

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